

How holistically is fisheries sustainability being assessed?

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Abstract

Sustainability in fisheries encompasses achieving environmental, social, and economic goals and requires appropriate governance. Several tools have been used to assess fisheries sustainability, with significant variation among them. Some of these tools solely address the 'environmental dimension' of sustainability but environmental outcomes may depend on how social and economic dimensions are addressed. To understand how existing tools to assess fisheries sustainability succeed or fail to integrate multiple dimensions of sustainability to achieve improved fisheries governance, we conducted a literature review through a search of key terms in Web of Science and Scopus databases. We evaluated the scope of the tool, i.e., which dimensions (environmental, social, economic), methods and indicators are considered; gaps in assessments; and if/how these approaches contribute to improve governance. In this talk, we will provide the preliminary results of this review together with a critical overview and benchmarking on the available tools for assessing and monitoring fisheries sustainability and the potential impacts generated in governance systems. We will also provide information on the gaps and limitations of current approaches to produce concrete actions towards fisheries sustainability.

